

Studies on the Behaviour of Cobalt and Calcium Soaps. Part-I. Solubility Studies in Non-aqueous Solvents

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Solubilities of laurates and oleates of calcium and cobalt have been measured in organic solvents at temperatures 35–60° and the same has been found to increase with the rise in temperature showing a marked change at Krafft point. The values of heat of solution, ΔH_s , and entropy of solution, $\Delta S_{s,0}$, have been calculated. These parameters suggest the presence of soap micelles in the solutions above Krafft point.

CALCIUM and cobalt laurates and oleates belong to a class of materials known as metallic soaps.

These soaps are characterised by a unique structure in that they combine in one molecule a non-polar organic radical with a polar carboxylic group having one hydrogen replaced by metal. It is the presence of these two dissimilar groups in a single molecule which accounts for the many interesting and commercially important applications for metallic soaps. Recently, the solubilities of calcium soaps have been measured with the help of metal complexing^{1,2} by phosphorus compounds and radiotracer technique³ involving ⁴⁵Ca. The solubility of cobalt laurate has been reported⁴ in aqueous potassium laurate solutions. Varma and Bhargava⁵ have measured the solubility of some lower fatty acid soaps of cobalt in aliphatic alcohols.

In the present communication, the solubility of calcium and cobalt soaps (*i.e.* laurates and oleates) has been studied in non-aqueous solvents at different temperatures (35–60°) with a view to ascertain the micellar aggregation of these soaps. It is felt that this information will be of distinct value in developing useful applications of these soaps.

Experimental

Reagent grade (Merck or B.D.H.) cobalt sulphate, calcium carbonate, fatty acids and solvents were used. The fatty acids were purified by distillation under reduced pressure. The b.p. of the solvents, purified by standard methods⁶, were methanol, 66°; butan-1-ol, 116–117°; 3-methyl-1-butanol, 129–130°; benzene 80°; and carbon tetrachloride, 76.5°.

The corresponding metal soaps were prepared by adding a hot solution of sodium soap to an aqueous solution of the metal salt, the former

being added dropwise with stirring at 50–5°. The precipitate was filtered off and washed with hot water. After initial drying in an air-oven (100–105°), final drying was carried out under reduced pressure. The soaps were analysed; percentages of respective metal contents: cobalt laurate, 12.85 (Calcd. 12.90), cobalt oleate, 9.43 (Calcd. 9.48), calcium laurate, 9.05 (Calcd. 9.15) and calcium oleate, 6.62% (Calcd. 6.65).

Procedure: Each saturated solution was prepared by agitation of an excess of soap in 25 ml stoppered wide mouth bottle and placed in a thermostatic bath at the required temperature ($\pm 0.05^\circ$). A clear supernatant saturated solution (5 ml) was taken only when the equilibrium was attained (after 3–5 h) at each temperature with pipette, evaporated near the boiling point of the solvent, dried and weighed.

Solubility (S_A) was calculated in g/1000 g solvent. Dilatometer was used⁷ to determine density (d) of the solvent with an accuracy of ± 0.000 g at different temperatures. Solubility (S) of the soap (mol. wt. m) in mol dm⁻³ was obtained⁸ from the relationship,

$$S = \frac{\frac{S_A}{m} \times 1000 \times d}{(1000 + S_A)}$$

Results and Discussion

The behaviour of calcium and cobalt soap solutions is caused by the amphipathic nature of soap molecules. Their solubilities vary in different solvents. Oleates do not dissolve appreciably in methanol. A comparison of the values shows that the solubility of calcium soaps are higher than cobalt soaps.

Solubility of soaps (Table 1) increases with increasing temperature. When the soap is heated in presence of a non-polar solvent, the opening of

TABLE 1—SOLUBILITY OF COBALT AND CALCIUM SOAPS IN ORGANIC SOLVENTS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Soap	Solubility (g/100 g)					
	35°	40°	45°	50°	55°	60°
Methanol						
Cobalt laurate	0.52	0.69	0.80	0.81	1.02	1.58
Calcium laurate	0.20	0.25	0.27	0.37	0.53	0.62
Butan-1-ol						
Cobalt laurate	0.18	0.21	0.26	0.44	0.62	1.04
Cobalt oleate	0.86	0.92	1.22	1.37	1.54	1.97
Calcium laurate	0.44	0.55	0.79	1.22	1.81	2.64
Calcium oleate	2.46	2.70	3.28	4.00	5.23	6.29
3-Methyl-butan-1-ol						
Cobalt laurate	1.30	1.41	1.49	1.61	4.18	6.59
Cobalt oleate	0.78	0.81	1.08	1.59	3.93	5.36
Calcium laurate	0.23	0.24	0.46	0.83	2.53	4.11
Calcium oleate	4.38	4.64	8.13	11.45	15.20	23.37
Carbon tetrachloride						
Cobalt laurate	0.21	0.38	0.41	0.54	1.06	1.49
Cobalt oleate	1.14	1.42	1.66	1.87	2.04	2.31
Calcium laurate	0.49	0.70	1.03	1.42	1.60	1.66
Calcium oleate	2.52	3.24	3.29	3.92	3.97	5.88
Benzene						
Cobalt laurate	0.22	0.39	0.54	0.75	1.02	1.08
Cobalt oleate	1.28	1.34	1.44	1.47	1.85	2.23
Calcium laurate	0.42	0.50	0.61	0.86	1.92	3.57
Calcium oleate	2.35	2.55	2.85	3.33	4.78	7.11

the lattice, resulting from the thermal agitation of the chains, permits entry between the chains of solvent molecules. The increased disorder in the lattice which results from this penetration causes a breakdown of the structure and the soap dissolves in the form of micelles⁹. When the solvent is polar it can also penetrate between the polar end groups of soap molecules. The lattice approaches its maximum degree of disorder at higher temperature. This results in swelling and finally dissolution in the solvents. The plots (Fig. 1) of $\log S$ vs $1/T$ show a marked change at a definite temperature (Table 2), indicating the existence of micelles above

TABLE 2—VALUES OF KRAFFT POINT OF SOAPS IN DIFFERENT ORGANIC SOLVENTS

Soap	K.p. (°C)				
	3-Methyl-butan-1-ol	Butan-1-ol	Methanol	Benzene	Carbon tetrachloride
Cobalt laurate	45	45	50	45	50
Cobalt oleate	45	45	—	50	45
Calcium laurate	40	45	50	50	50
Calcium oleate	40	45	—	50	50

this temperature known as Krafft point. In general, the Krafft point in methanol, benzene and carbon tetrachloride are higher than other solvents.

 Fig. 1. Plot of $\log S$ vs $1/T$ of cobalt laurate.

It is evident that at low temperature range, the solubility of the soap is small but increases gradually and the increase is enormous at the Krafft point. This remarkable increase in solubility can be explained as the single molecule of soap is relatively less soluble than the micelle of the soap. The possibility of solute-solvent interaction between hydrophobic ends of the soap ions and the alcohols which may be the cause of high solubility has also been examined by viscosity measurement¹⁰. It is observed that no solute-solvent interaction occurs but the soap forms micellar aggregates in the solution.

The apparent heat of solution (ΔH_s) can be calculated¹¹ by the relation,

$$\Delta H_s = RT^2 \left[\frac{d \ln S}{dT} \right] \quad (1)$$

where, S is the solubility in mol dm⁻³ and other terms have their usual meaning.

The plots (Fig. 1) of $\log S$ vs $1/T$ are characterised by intersection of two straight lines at a point corresponding to Krafft point. The value of ΔH_s have been calculated from the slopes of the linear plots and recorded in Table 3. These values are found to differ appreciably below and above Krafft point which confirm the micelle formation in these solvents. It is found that ΔH_s values of cobalt soaps are higher than that of calcium soaps above Krafft point, but in benzene the behaviour is otherwise.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF ΔH_S OF SOAPS IN ORGANIC SOLVENTS

Soap	ΔH_S (kcal mol ⁻¹)									
	3-Methylbutan-1-ol		Butan-1-ol		Methanol		Benzene		Carbon tetrachloride	
	Above K.p.	Below K.p.	Above K.p.	Below K.p.	Above K.p.	Below K.p.	Above K.p.	Below K.p.	Above K.p.	Below K.p.
Cobalt laurate	29.34	3.66	18.79	5.95	14.21	4.12	7.33	22.08	21.54	8.71
Cobalt oleate	22.00	6.41	9.62	3.75	—	—	5.50	0.91	3.66	7.78
Calcium laurate	29.05	1.37	16.96	6.87	12.83	7.79	31.17	8.71	1.83	12.38
Calcium oleate	16.50	1.37	5.50	4.58	—	—	14.67	5.04	2.75	5.50

TABLE 4—VALUES OF ΔS_{soi} OF SOAPS IN ORGANIC SOLVENTS

Temp. K	ΔS_{soi} ($\times 10^3$ kcal mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)				
	3-Methylbutan-1-ol	Butan-1-ol	Methanol	Benzene	Carbon tetrachloride
Cobalt laurate					
308	1.19	1.34	1.34	7.17	2.83
313	1.17	1.32	1.32	7.05	2.78
318	—	—	1.30	—	2.74
323	9.08	5.82	—	2.27	—
328	8.94	5.73	4.33	2.24	6.57
333	8.10	5.64	4.28	2.20	6.47
Cobalt oleate					
308	2.08	1.22	—	0.30	2.53
313	2.05	1.20	—	0.29	2.48
318	—	—	—	0.29	—
323	0.68	2.98	—	1.68	1.13
328	0.67	2.93	—	1.68	1.12
333	0.66	2.89	—	1.65	1.10
Calcium laurate					
308	0.45	2.23	2.53	2.83	4.02
313	—	2.20	2.49	2.78	3.95
318	9.51	—	2.45	2.74	3.89
323	9.36	5.25	—	—	—
328	9.22	5.17	3.91	9.50	0.56
333	9.08	5.09	3.85	9.36	0.55
Calcium oleate					
308	0.45	1.49	—	1.64	1.78
313	—	1.46	—	1.61	1.76
318	5.19	—	—	1.59	1.73
323	5.11	1.70	—	—	—
328	5.03	1.68	—	4.47	0.84
333	4.96	1.65	—	4.40	0.83

$$\Delta S_{soi} = \frac{\Delta H_S}{T} \quad (2)$$

A perusal of Table 4 indicates a remarkable change in ΔS_{soi} values at Krafft point. It is seen that the values of ΔS_{soi} for calcium soaps below Krafft point are lower than the values above this temperature, while in carbon tetrachloride the values are higher. In case of cobalt soaps, the values for laurate are lower and oleate are higher below Krafft point, but the same in benzene show a reverse behaviour.

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References

1. R. R. IRANI and C. F. CALLIS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1960, 64, 1741.
2. R. R. IRANI, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1962, 7, 580.
3. J. Y. YOKE, III, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, 62, 753.
4. W. U. MALIK and A. K. JAIN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1967, 29, 2825.
5. R. P. VARMA and H. K. BHARGAVA, *Ann. Chim.*, 1976, 66, 773.
6. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 3rd. ed., Longmans, London, 1971, p. 163.
7. R. P. VARMA and K. KUMAR, *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 156.
8. A. WEISSBERGER, "Technique of Organic Chemistry", 3rd. ed., Interscience, New York, 1959, Vol. I, Part I, p. 658.
9. E. P. MARTIN and R. C. PINK, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1750.
10. R. P. VARMA and P. K. JAIN, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1982, 27, 1117.
11. W. U. MALIK and S. I. AHMAD, *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 42, 454.

Since the process of solution of soaps in organic solvents can be considered an isothermal equilibrium reaction, the free energy change is zero. The entropy of solution (ΔS_{soi}) can be calculated as